

PARACHOR AND RING STRUCTURE. PART II

BY W. V. BHAGWAT AND S. O. SHUKLA

It is suggested that bridge-ring may be considered to be equivalent to three rings and not two rings. It is shown that in case of *o*-toluquinone the tautomerism between simple and bridge ring does exist unlike the conclusion of Sugden. Further phorone and its derivatives which form dicyclic structure should contain one ring of three and one of four and not one of three and one of five. The same is true of distyryl ketone. Hence dichloro derivatives of phorone seem mainly to be bicyclic in form unlike the conclusions of Sugden.

Most of the reactions of *p*-quinones are represented by the formula (I) but Grabe (*Annalen*, 1868, 140, 1), Binder (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1921), Hartley and Leonard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 34) and Hankh (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1910, 82, 546) prefer the peroxide formula (II).

Sugden ("Parachor and Valency," p. 46) comparing his parachor values of benzoquinone and toluquinone in fused state concludes that they should have diketone structure (I) and that if tautomerism between (I) and (II) occurs then the amount of (II) present in fused state is very small.

Sugden considers that the peroxide structure is in one plane and hence contribution is due to two rings of six only. In our opinion if the structure is considered in space then the contribution due to three rings,

must be added. The calculated parachor for peroxide formula is therefore to be increased by 67. The results still favour the diketone structure, but they no doubt support the view that tautomerism between the forms (I) and (II) does exist even in the fused state, specially in the case of toluquinone and that at least 28% of the substance are in peroxide form, even at the temperature of fusion. It is not unlikely that at ordinary temperature the view of Grabe and others (*loc. cit.*) is more correct. The deviation in part may be due to the fact that the additive nature of ring structure shown in Part I may not be exactly true, as all the three rings are not identical six-membered rings.

Another structural problem is the tautomerism of the derivatives of phorone studied by Francis and Wilson and by Ingold and Shoppy (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 2238; 1928, 365, 1662, 1866). If substituents X and X' are introduced into α -position in the phorone molecule, a rearrangement of valencies may take place to give bicyclic structure. If,

however, one of the substituent groups is of the form YO a monocyclic structure may result as shown below :—

Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 490) has compared the calculated and observed values for various substituents in X and Y position.

In case of bridge-ring structure Sugden (*loc. cit.*) assumes that they are equivalent to two rings, one of five and one of three members. Whether the structure is considered in space or in one plane, there is one ring of three and one of four. Hence the difference between open chain and ring structure for bicyclic formula for the calculated values of parachor should be $P(\text{ring of three}) + P(\text{ring of four}) - 2P(\text{double bond})$. This is equal to $16.7 + 11.6 - 46.4 = 18.1$ and not 21.4 as calculated by Sugden. In a similar manner difference between monocyclic structure and open chain structure is -14.7 . When both types of rings are possible and the value lies between the two, -18.1 and -14.7 , it is difficult to choose between the two, since both values are so near each other. The difference for dichlorophorone is -18.9 . This in our view clearly indicates that it is in all probability bicyclic in structure and not a tautomeric mixture of isomerides represented by the structures :

In other cases when the Y-group is of the type OY, all values indicate bicyclic structure although Ingold and Shoppe (*loc. cit.*) believe that all of them have monocyclic structure on chemical grounds.

Derivatives of distyryl ketone show similar bicyclic change. Thus dibromodistyryl ketone gives an anomaly of -13.1 very near to -18.1 indicating the predominance of the bicyclic form. In this case also Sugden assumes the existence of one ring of three and one of five. As stated above there is one ring of three and one of four members.

